

GenAI Assessment Rubric – FPCEE Blanquerna

CoARA pilot project
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Overview and Development of the GenAI Assessment Rubric – FPCEE Blanquerna

The FPCEE–Blanquerna GenAI Assessment Rubric was developed to evaluate researchers’ research production, quality, and relevance through the Narrative CV. By providing structured criteria across five assessment modules, the rubric promotes a consistent, transparent, and comprehensive evaluation of researchers’ activities and achievements.

The rubric is organised into modules aligned with the Narrative CV structure, each representing a major domain of research contribution. Within each module, evaluation criteria are structured hierarchically into dimensions, categories, and items, with each item assigned a relative weight (value) reflecting its importance within the overall assessment. This structure specifies the types of contributions that can be reported and assessed through the Narrative CV, while allowing sufficient flexibility to accommodate disciplinary diversity and heterogeneous research trajectories (Table 1 details the rubric’s structure into dimensions and categories)

The development of the rubric followed an iterative, expert-informed process. Initial versions were designed through structured discussions among research assessment experts involved in the project. These versions were subsequently tested and refined using Narrative CVs from researchers at different career stages (R1–R4), enabling the calibration of criteria and weights across diverse profiles and moments of academic development.

We were concerned to develop an assessment tool, the rubric, explicitly aligned with the European Framework for Research Careers (R1–R4). Thus, within each career stage, we indicate what is expected and enable evaluators to mark whether a given item applies, does not apply, or is not expected but is recognised as a positive bonus when present. Each assessed item must be supported by a verbatim citation from the Narrative CV and, when relevant, by additional evidence or links, whose reliability is considered as part of the evaluation.

Each module includes qualitative feedback fields that allow evaluators to summarise key strengths, identify areas for improvement, and note contextual considerations. Designed to support both human evaluators and the training and deployment of the GenAI decision-support model, the rubric provides a reliable and transparent framework that tightly links narrative reporting, qualitative judgement, and career-stage sensitivity.

Table 1
Dimensions and categories included in the GenAI Assessment Rubric – FPCEE Blanquerna

Dimensions	Categories
Knowledge Generation	Publications
	Publication Metadata
	Methodological Contributions
	Intangible assets (softwares, patents, etc.)

Researcher Training Capacity, Teamwork, and Working Relationships	Principal Investigator (PI) of Competitive Research Projects
	Participation in Competitive Research Projects
	Doctoral Thesis Supervision
	Leadership
	Promotion of Inclusive Policies
	Interdisciplinary Collaborations
	Collaborations with Other Research Teams

Contributions to the Scientific and Innovation Community	Participation in International Research Networks
	Participation in National Research Networks
	Editorial Board Membership (Editor-in-Chief or Associate Editor)
	Participation in Institutional Committees
	Participation in Evaluation Committees
Scientific Dissemination Activities	

Contributions to Society	Knowledge Transfer Contracts
	Knowledge Transfer Activities
	Collaboration with External Institutions

Trajectory Assessment	Coherence (Self-Assessment vs. Evidence; Individual vs. Group Alignment)
	Strategic Vision
	Self-Critique

For a detailed description of the FPCEE–Blanquerna GenAI Assessment Rubric, see:
[Final GenAI Assessment Rubric – FPCEE Blanquerna](#)